

Applications of Matching in Bipartite Graph

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to study lattice graphs which are readily seen to have many perfect matchings and considers application of matching in bipartite graph, such as the optimal assignment problem. Assignment problem is an important subject discussed in real physical world. We endeavor in this paper to introduce a new approach to assignment problem namely, ones assignment method, for solving a wide range of such problems. This method offers significant advantages over similar methods, in the process, first we define the assignment matrix, then by using determinant representation we obtain a reduced matrix which has at least one 1 in each row and column. Then by using the new method, we obtain an optimal solution for assignment problem by assigning ones to each row and each column. The new method is based on creating some ones in the assignment matrix and then try to find a complete assignment to there ones. The proposed method is a systematic procedure, easy to apply and can be utilized for all types of assignment problem with maximize or minimize objective functions. At the end, this method is illustrated with some numerical examples.

Key words: bipartite graph, weighted bipartite matching problem, perfect matchings, ones assignment method

Introduction

When speaking of graphs we might think about pictures of some kind that are used to represent information such as bar graphs, flow charts and graphs of functions. But the graphs we shall discuss are quite different. They correspond more closely with the objects which, in everyday language that we call “networks”.

Our specific interest in this research paper is matching problems. As an illustration, consider the following problem: A company wants to hire a number of employees in various positions. For each position employee pair, the salary depends on the position and the employee qualification. Each position should be occupied with only one employee, and any employee should only be employed in only one position.

The problem is how to find an assignment of the employees to the positions, so that the total salary is minimized for the company. The problem can be converted to a "**minimum weight matching**" in graph theory. The assignment problem is a weighted bipartite matching problem, where the costs are the weights.

Assignment of people or other resources to various workstations or certain equipment to accomplish certain tasks while minimizing the total cost is a frequent management decision problem. For example, assigning employees to various tasks, teachers to different classes, crews to projects, and ambulances to first-aid stations are good real-world examples of assignment problems. The basic goal of the assignment problem is either to minimize the total cost of completing all the required tasks or to maximize the total payoff (or benefits) from the assignments. This iterative method is based on add or subtract a constant to every element of a row or column of the cost matrix, in a minimization model and create some zeros in the given cost matrix and then try to find a complete assignment in terms of zeros. By a complete assignment for a cost matrix $n \times n$, we mean an assignment plan containing exactly n assigned independent zeros, one in each row and one in each column. The main concept of assignment problem is to find the optimum allocation of a number of resources to an equal number of demand points. An assignment plan is optimal if optimizes the total cost or effectiveness of doing all the jobs.

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This research paper attempts to propose a method for solving assignment problem which is different from the preceding methods.

Background Materials

This research paper mostly follows the terminology in the textbook *Introduction to Graph Theory* by West.

Basic Concepts

A **graph** G with n vertices and m edges consists of a **vertex set** $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ and an **edge set** $E(G) = \{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$, where each edge consists of two (possibly equal) vertices in $V(G)$ called its **endpoints**. We usually write $G = (V(G), E(G))$, or simply $G = (V, E)$. A **directed graph** or **digraph** G consists of a vertex set $V(G)$ and an edge set $E(G)$, where each edge is an ordered pair of vertices.

A **loop** is an edge whose endpoints are equal. **Parallel edges** or **multiple edges** are edges that have the same pair of endpoints. A **simple graph** is a graph having no loops or multiple edges. A **complete graph** is a simple graph in which every pair of vertices is an edge. Denote a complete graph with n vertices by K_n .

Figure 1. A pictorial representation of a graph

A graph is finite if its vertex set and edge set are finite. We emphasize here that every graph mentioned in this paper is finite.

A typical example of a simple graph $G = (V, E)$ is given by the sets $V = \{a, b, c, d, z\}$, $E = \{(a, b), (a, d), (b, z), (c, d), (d, z)\}$.

We represent the vertices as points, and join two points by a line whenever the corresponding pair of vertices is an edge. Thus Figure 1.1 is a pictorial (or graphical) representation of the graph given in the example above.

A **walk of length k** is a sequence $v_0, e_1, v_1, e_2, \dots, e_k, v_k$ of vertices and edges such that $e_i = v_{i-1}v_i$ for all i . A **path** is a walk with no repeated vertex. A **trail** is a walk with no repeated edge. A walk (or trail) is **closed** if it has length at least one and its endpoints are equal. A walk $v_0, e_1, v_1, e_2, \dots, e_k, v_k$ whose vertices are all distinct except that $v_0 = v_k$ is called a **cycle**. We call a cycle **odd** if it has an odd number of distinct vertices (and an odd number of edges).

A walk specifies a route in G which proceeds through a sequence of vertices joined by edges. A walk may visit any vertex an arbitrary number of times. In a path, each vertex is visited at most once. A **u, v -path** is a path whose first vertex is u and last vertex is v .

A graph G is **bipartite** if $V(G)$ is the union of two disjoint sets X and Y such that each edge consists of one vertex from X and one vertex from Y . We say G is a bipartite graph with bipartition X, Y . Here is an important fact about bipartite graphs.

Theorem. *A graph G is bipartite if and only if it contains no odd cycles.*

This Theorem implies that whenever a graph G is not bipartite, we can prove this statement by presenting an odd cycle in G .

Matchings

Matchings in Bipartite Graphs

A **matching of size k** in a graph G is a set of k pairwise disjoint edges. The vertices belonging to the edges of a matching are **saturated** by the matching; the others are **unsaturated**. If a matching saturates every vertex of G , then it is a **perfect matching**. A **maximum matching** is a matching of maximum size.

Figure 2. A matching M_1 and a perfect matching M_2

In Figure 2 two matchings M_1 and M_2 in the same bipartite graph are illustrated; the edges which belong to the matchings are indicated by dashed lines. In particular, M_2 is a perfect matching.

Given a matching M , an **M -alternating path** is a path that alternates between edges in M and edges not in M . An M -alternating path P that begins and ends at M -unsaturated vertices is an **M -augmenting path**, replacing $M \cap E(P)$ by $E(P) - M$ produces a new matching M' with one more edge than M . Maximum matchings are characterized by the absence of augmenting path, which was proven by in 1957.

Theorem: (Berge) *A matching M in a graph (not necessarily bipartite) G is a maximum matching in G if and only if G has no M -augmenting path.*

For any $s \subseteq X$, let $N(S)$ denote the set of vertices having a neighbor in S .

If a matching M saturates X , it must be true that $|N(S)| \geq |S|$. This is known as Hall's condition. In 1935, the mathematician Philip Hall proved that this obvious necessary condition is also sufficient.

Theorem: (Hall) *If G is a bipartite graph with bipartition X, Y , then G has a matching M that saturates X if and only if $|N(S)| \geq |S|$ for all $s \subseteq X$.*

When the sets of the bipartition have the same size, i.e., $|X| = |Y|$, then G has a perfect matching under Hall's condition.

Corollary: If G is a bipartite graph with bipartition X, Y and $|X| = |Y|$, then G has a perfect matching if and only if $|N(S)| \geq |S|$ for all $S \subseteq X$.

Example: We set $X = \{ 1, 2, 3 \}$, $Y = \{ a, b, c \}$ and $M = \{ (1, a), (2, b), (3, c) \}$.

We also have

$$\begin{aligned}
 S = \{ 1 \}, N(S) &= \{ a, b \} \text{ and } |N(S)| > |S|. & S = \{ 2 \}, N(S) &= \{ b \} \text{ and } |N(S)| = |S|. \\
 S = \{ 3 \}, N(S) &= \{ a, b, c \} \text{ and } |N(S)| > |S|. & S = \{ 1, 2 \}, N(S) &= \{ a, b \} \text{ and } |N(S)| = |S|. \\
 S = \{ 1, 3 \}, N(S) &= \{ a, b, c \} \text{ and } |N(S)| > |S|. & S = \{ 2, 3 \}, N(S) &= \{ a, b, c \} \text{ and } |N(S)| > |S|. \\
 S = \{ 1, 2, 3 \}, N(S) &= \{ a, b, c \} \text{ and } |N(S)| = |S|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we obtain G has a perfect matching from X to Y if and only if $|N(S)| \geq |S|$ for all $S \subseteq X$.

Applications of Matching in Bipartite Graph

Mathematical Formulation of Assignment Problem

Mathematically an assignment problem can be stated as follows:

$$\text{Optimize} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} x_{ij} \tag{1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{subject to} \quad & \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = 1, & i &= 1, \dots, n \\
 & \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} = 1, & j &= 1, \dots, n \\
 & x_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } 1, & i &= 1, \dots, n ; j = 1, \dots, n
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where c_{ij} is the cost or effectiveness of assigning i^{th} job to j^{th} machine, and x_{ij} is to be some positive integer or zero, and the only possible integer is one, so the condition of $x_{ij} = 0$ or 1, is automatically satisfied. Associated to each assignment problem there is a matrix called cost or effectiveness matrix $[c_{ij}]$ where c_{ij} is the cost of assigning i^{th} job to j^{th} facility.

In this paper we call it assignment matrix, and represent it as follows:

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 & 1 & 2 & 3 & \dots & n \\
 \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ n \end{array} & \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} & \dots & c_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & c_{n3} & \dots & c_{nn} \end{array} \right)
 \end{array}$$

which is always a square matrix, thus each task can be assigned to only one machine.

In fact any solution of this assignment problem will contain exactly n non-zero positive individual allocations.

A customary and convenient method, termed as “assignment algorithm” has been developed for such problems. This iterative method is known as Hungarian assignment method. It is based on add or subtract a constant to every element of a row or column of the cost matrix in a minimization model, and create some zeros in the given cost matrix and then try to find a complete assignment in terms of zeros. In fact our aim is to create ones in place of zeroes, and try to assign them in our problem.

A New Approach for Solving Assignment Problem

This section presents a new method to solve the assignment problem which is different from the preceding method. We call it “one- assignment method”, because of making assignment in terms of ones.

The new method is based on creating some ones in the assignment matrix and then tries to find a complete assignment in terms of ones. By a complete assignment we mean an assignment plan containing exactly n assigned independent ones, one in each row and one in each column.

Now, consider the assignment matrix where c_{ij} is the cost or effectiveness of assigning i^{th} job to j^{th} machine.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 & 1 & 2 & 3 & \dots & n \\
 \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ n \end{array} & \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} & \dots & c_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & c_{n3} & \dots & c_{nn} \end{array} \right)
 \end{array}$$

The new algorithm is as follows:

Let (1-2) be an assignment problem in which the objective function can be minimized or maximized.

Step 1: In a minimization (maximization) case, find the minimum (maximum) element of each row in the assignment matrix (say a_i) and write it on the right hand side of the matrix.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 & 1 & 2 & 3 & \dots & n \\
 \begin{array}{c} \left(\\ \left| \\ \left| \\ \left| \\ \left(\end{array} & \begin{array}{ccccc} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} & \dots & c_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & c_{n3} & \dots & c_{nn} \end{array} & \begin{array}{c} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \end{array}
 \end{array}$$

Then divide each element of i^{th} row of the matrix by a_i . These operations create at least one ones in each rows.

In term of ones for each row and column do assignment, otherwise go to Step 2.

Step 2: Find the minimum (maximum) element of each column in assignment matrix (say b_j), and write it below j^{th} column. Then divide each element of j^{th} column of the matrix by b_j . These operations create at least one ones in each columns. Make assignment in terms of ones. If no feasible assignment can be achieved from Steps (1) and (2) then go to Step 3.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 & 1 & 2 & 3 & \dots & n \\
 \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ n \end{array} & \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} c_{11}/a_1 & c_{12}/a_1 & c_{13}/a_1 & \dots & c_{1n}/a_1 \\ c_{21}/a_2 & c_{22}/a_2 & c_{23}/a_2 & \dots & c_{2n}/a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{n1}/a_n & c_{n2}/a_n & c_{n3}/a_n & \dots & c_{nn}/a_n \end{array} \right) \\
 & b_1 & b_2 & b_3 & \dots & b_n
 \end{array}$$

Step 3: Draw the minimum number of lines to cover all the ones of the matrix. If the number of drawn lines less than n , then the complete assignment is not possible, while if the number of lines is exactly equal to n , then the complete assignment is obtained.

Step 4: If a complete assignment program is not possible in Step 3, then select the smallest (largest) element (say d_{ij}) out of those which do not lie on any of the lines in the above matrix. Then divide by d_{ij} each element of the uncovered rows or columns, which d_{ij} lies on it. This operation create some new ones to this row or column. If still a complete optimal assignment is not achieved in this new matrix, then use Steps 4 and 3 iteratively. By repeating the same procedure the optimal assignment will be obtained.

Priority, plays an important role in this method, when we want to assign the ones.

Priority rule: For maximization (minimization) assignment problem, assign the ones on the rows which have greatest (smallest) element on the right hand side, respectively.

One question arise here, what to do with non square matrix? To make square, a non square matrix, we add one artificial row or column which all elements are one. Thus we solve the problem with the new matrix, by using the new method. The matrix after performing the steps reduces to a matrix which has ones in each rows and columns. So, the optimal assignment has been reached.

Numerical Examples

The following examples may be helpful to clarify the proposed method:

Example: Consider the following assignment problem. An educational center has got five expert TV programmers. The center needs five educational programs to be developed. The head of an educational center, after studying carefully the programs to be developed, estimates the computer time in minutes required by the experts to the educational programs as follows:

Only one expert can be assigned to each program, is presented in Table 4.1. Notice that there are the same number of rows (programmers) and columns (programs). Also, the amount of supply and demand for each row and each column is exactly one.

Table 1. Tableau form of the assignment problem

Programmers	Programs					Supply
	A	B	C	D	E	
1	12	8	7	15	4	1
2	7	9	1	14	10	1
3	9	6	12	6	7	1
4	7	6	14	6	10	1
5	9	6	12	10	6	1
Demand	1	1	1	1	1	5

In Table 1, assign the programmers to the programs in such a way that the total computer time is least.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 A \quad B \quad C \quad D \quad E \\
 1 \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 12 & 8 & 7 & 15 & 4 \end{array} \right) \\
 2 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 7 & 9 & 1 & 14 & 10 \end{array} \right| \\
 3 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 9 & 6 & 12 & 6 & 7 \end{array} \right| \\
 4 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 7 & 6 & 14 & 6 & 10 \end{array} \right| \\
 5 \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 9 & 6 & 12 & 10 & 6 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array}$$

Find the minimum element of each row in the assignment matrix (say a_i) and write it on the right hand side of the matrix, as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 A \quad B \quad C \quad D \quad E \quad min \\
 1 \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 12 & 8 & 7 & 15 & 4 \end{array} \right) 4 \\
 2 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 7 & 9 & 1 & 14 & 10 \end{array} \right| 1 \\
 3 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 9 & 6 & 12 & 6 & 7 \end{array} \right| 6 \\
 4 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 7 & 6 & 14 & 6 & 10 \end{array} \right| 6 \\
 5 \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 9 & 6 & 12 & 10 & 6 \end{array} \right) 6
 \end{array}$$

Then divide each element of i^{th} row of the matrix by a_i . These operations create ones to each rows, and the matrix reduces to following matrix.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 A \quad B \quad C \quad D \quad E \quad min \\
 1 \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 3 & 2 & 7/4 & 15/4 & 1 \end{array} \right) 4 \\
 2 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 7 & 9 & 1 & 14 & 10 \end{array} \right| 1 \\
 3 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 3/2 & 1 & 2 & 1 & 7/6 \end{array} \right| 6 \\
 4 \left| \begin{array}{ccccc} 7/6 & 1 & 7/3 & 1 & 5/3 \end{array} \right| 6 \\
 5 \left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 3/2 & 1 & 2 & 5/3 & 1 \end{array} \right) 6
 \end{array}$$

Now find the minimum element of each column in assignment matrix (say b_j), and write it below that column. Then divide each element of j^{th} column of the matrix by b_j .

	A	B	C	D	E	min	
1	3	2	7/4	15/4	1	4	}
2	7	9	1	14	10	1	
3	3/2	1	2	1	7/6	6	
4	7/6	1	7/3	1	5/3	6	
5	3/2	1	2	5/3	1	6	
min 7/6 1 1 1 1							

	A	B	C	D	E	min	
1	18/7	2	7/4	15/4	1	4	}
2	6	9	1	14	10	1	
3	18/14	1	2	1	7/6	6	
4	1	1	7/3	1	5/3	6	
5	18/14	1	2	5/3	1	6	
min 7/6 1 1 1 1							

The minimum number of lines required to pass through all the ones of the matrix is 5.

(18/7	2	7/4	15/4	1)
	6	9	1	14	10	
	18/14	1	2	1	7/6	
	1	1	7/3	1	5/3	
	18/14	1	2	5/3	1)

	A	B	C	D	E	min	
1	18/7	2	7/4	15/4	1	4	}
2	6	9	1	14	10	1	
3	18/14	1	2	1	7/6	6	
4	1	1	7/3	1	5/3	6	
5	18/14	1	2	5/3	1	6	

So, the complete assignment is possible, and we can assign the ones and an optimal assignment is as follows:

Table 2. The optimal assignment of the assignment problem

Optimal Assignment		
Programmers	Programs	Time
1	E	4
2	C	1
3	D	6
4	A	7
5	B	6
Total Time		24 min

Example: A small machining shop has 5 machinists available to assign to jobs for the day. Five jobs are offered with expected profit for each machinist on each job as follows:

Machinist	Jobs				
	A	B	C	D	E
1	5	11	10	12	4
2	2	4	6	3	5
3	3	12	5	14	6
4	6	14	4	11	7
5	7	9	8	12	5

Find the assignment of machinists to jobs that will result in a maximum profit.

Step 1: Find the maximum element of each row in the assignment matrix (say a_i) and write it on the right hand side of the matrix, as follows:

	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>max</i>
1	5	11	10	12	4	12
2	2	4	6	3	5	6
3	3	12	5	14	6	14
4	6	14	4	11	7	14
5	7	9	8	12	5	12

Then divide each element of i^{th} row of the matrix by a_i . These operations create ones to each rows, and the matrix reduces to following matrix.

	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>max</i>
1	0.42	0.92	0.83	1	0.33	12
2	0.33	0.66	1	0.5	0.83	6
3	0.21	0.86	0.36	1	0.43	14
4	0.43	1	0.28	0.78	0.5	14
5	0.58	0.75	0.66	1	0.46	12

Step 2: Since we can not make assignment in terms of the ones, now find the maximum element of each column in assignment matrix (say b_j), and write it below that column. Then divide each element of j^{th} column of the matrix by b_j .

These operations create ones to each columns, and matrix reduces to following matrix, feasible assignment can not be secured from Steps (1) and (2) so, go to Step 3.

	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>max</i>
1	0.42	0.92	0.83	1	0.33	12
2	0.33	0.66	1	0.5	0.83	6
3	0.21	0.86	0.36	1	0.43	14
4	0.43	1	0.28	0.78	0.5	14
5	0.58	0.75	0.66	1	0.46	12
<i>max</i>	0.58	0.92	1	1	0.83	

Step 3: Draw the minimum number of lines required to pass through all the ones of the matrix. Clearly the four lines are passing through all the ones. Since the number of lines is not equal to the order of the matrix, the optimal assignment has not been reached.

$$\left(\begin{array}{ccc|cc} 0.71 & 0.92 & 0.83 & 1 & 0.4 \\ 0.57 & 0.66 & 1 & 0.5 & 1 \\ 0.32 & 0.86 & 0.36 & 1 & 0.51 \\ 0.73 & 1 & 0.28 & 0.78 & 0.6 \\ 1 & 0.75 & 0.66 & 1 & 0.5 \end{array} \right)$$

We perform the Step 4.

Step 4. Select the largest element (say d_{ij}) out of those which do not lie on any of the lines in the above matrix. It is in the third column $d_{ij} = 0.83$.

Then divide each element of the third column, which d_{ij} is on it. This operation creates a new one to this column.

	A	B	C	D	E	max
1	0.71	0.92	1	1	0.4	12
2	0.57	0.66	1.2	0.5	1	6
3	0.32	0.86	0.43	1	0.51	14
4	0.73	1	0.34	0.78	0.6	14
5	1	0.75	0.79	1	0.5	12

Now, we can assign the ones, it is based on priority rule. Priority rule is assigning one on the rows which have greatest element on the right hand side, respectively.

The details of this program are as follows:

- Machinist 3 assigns to job D: profit 14.
- Machinist 4 assigns to job B: profit 14.
- Machinist 5 assigns to job A: profit 7.
- Machinist 1 assigns to job C: profit 10.
- Machinist 2 assigns to job E: profit 5.

So the optimal assignment has been reached, and total profit according to this assignment schedule will be 50.

Conclusion

In this research paper, a new and simple method was introduced for solving weighted bipartite matching problem. This method can be used for all kinds of assignment problems, whether maximize or minimize objective function. The new method is based on creating some ones in the assignment matrix, and find an assignment in terms of the ones.

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